

A Report About:

Analysis Of Corvid-19's Impact on Zara Revenue In Light Of
Strategic Management Theories

SUAAD AALTHANI

Abstract

Purpose: This report analyses the impact of Corvid-19 on Zara revenue during 2020 and 2021. There are three Strategic Management Theoretical Tools used in this study: Porter's Five Forces Model and External Factor Analysis Summary (EFAS) for assessing the external factors affecting Zara's revenue. Also, a Valuable, Rare, Inimitable, and Organizationally Oriented (VIRO) framework and Internal Factor Analysis Summary (IFAS) analyze the internal factors. Finally, the Strategic Factor Analysis Summary (SFAS) matrix evaluates both internal and external factors.

Methodology: This report uses several types of ProQuest literature (e-books and e-journals) to analyze the issue and implement analysis tools. Furthermore, this report used online magazines, press articles and e-journals from multiple sources to collect relevant data on the latest news and statistics.

Results: The Strategic Management Theoretical Tools show that Zara has a poor response to the current situation and recommends focusing on formulating the current strategy using the Strategic Factor Analysis Summary (SFAS) Matrix. Additionally, the report recommends social media advertising to neutralize the negative impact of Corvid-19 on revenue and strengthen brand loyalty.

Keywords: Strategic Management, Vertical Integration, Porter's Five Forces Model, External Factor Analysis Summary (EFAS), Valuable, Rare, Inimitable, and Organizational-oriented (VIRO) framework, Internal Factor Analysis Summary (IFAS), Strategic Factor Analysis Summary (SFAS) Matrix, Competitive advantages, Intangible, and tangible resources.

CONTENTS

1. Introduction.....	4
1.1 General Background.....	4
1.2 Report Objective.....	4
1. External Environment.....	4
2. Internal Environment.....	4
1.3 Methodology.....	5
1.4 Structure.....	5
Section 1: Zara's vision, mission, current strategy, and revenue for the past three years are examined.....	6
1.1 Vision.....	6
1.2 Mission.....	6
1.3 Current Strategy.....	6
1.4 Zara's last three years revenue.....	6
Section 2: External Environment Analysis.....	7
2.1 Porter's Five Forces Model summarized by Porter (1979) and its contribution to Zara.....	7
2.2 Strategic Factor Analysis Summary (SFAS) Matrix (adopted from (Jeyarathmm, 2007).....	12
Section 3 Zara's Internal Environment.....	14
3.1 Resources.....	14
3.1.1 Tangible Resources:.....	14
3.1.2 Intangible Resources:.....	15
3.2 Capabilities.....	16
3.3 Evaluate Zara's Key Resources and Capabilities.....	17
3.3.1 Valuable, Rare, Inimitable, and Organizational-oriented (VIRO) framework:.....	17
3.3.2 Internal Factors Evaluation Summary (IFES).....	19
3.3.3 Strategic Factors Evaluation Summary.....	20
Section 4 Strategic management tools implications and Recommendations:.....	22
4.1 implications:.....	22
4.2 Recommendations:.....	22
5. Conclusion:.....	23
6. Bibliography.....	24

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 General Background

Zara is a leading international fashion company. This company is part of Inditex, one of the world's largest distribution groups. [\(ZARA, 2022\)](#). Zara was founded in 1963; the business was based in A Coruña, northwest Spain. Originally, Confecciones GOA was a modest workshop making dresses and quilted dressing gowns for distribution. In ten years, the workforce has grown to 500 employees. Founder Amancio Ortega opened Zara's first store in 1975 after making textiles for 12 years. Zara's business model in 1967 shrinks the distance between fashion makers and consumers, bringing them closer than ever to the products they want at an affordable price. As of 1983, Zara has nine stores in some of Spain's most prestigious shopping districts. Inditex was officially founded in 1985. In 1988, Zara opened its first international store in Porto, Portugal, then in New York in 1989. By the end of 2010, Zara had sold its products online in 16 European markets. In addition to opening our 5,000th store, Zara presented Its new Environmental Strategy Plan, Sustainable Inditex 2011-2015.

1.2 Report Objective

By the end of 2019, Zara's digital and sustainability transformation was the highest priority strategic goal in response to Corvid-19's impacts on the apparel industry. Therefore, digital transformation is driving major renovations to nearly every store network and introducing cutting-edge technology in every aspect of its business model. 2020 was an important year for the progress of the digital transformation strategy initiated in 2012, built around the integrated store and online sales platform driven by the covid-19 pandemic, which always underscored the health of its staff and customers. Today, Inditex has more than 7,000 stores, including [2,000 stores](#) [\(Statista, 2022\)](#) only for Zara worldwide. Also, Zara will contribute 69.25% of the [Net sales share of the Inditex Group worldwide in 2020](#) [\(Statista, 2022\)](#) . Even though Zara tried to face the challenge, the negative impacts on Zara were more than even Zara's expectations, causing a dramatic decline in Zara revenue in 2020 & 2021. Declining revenue is a significant business strategic issue that requires analysis. Thus, this report is going to analyze the internal and external factors that impacted the company revenue and the level of the company's response to these factors using the below tools:

1. External Environment
 - 1.1 Porter's Five Forces Model
 - 1.2 External Factor Analysis Summary (EFAS)

2. Internal Environment
 - 1.1 Valuable, Rare, Inimitable, and Organizational-oriented (VIRO) framework
 - 1.2 Internal Factor Analysis Summary (IFAS)

Also, this report will discuss the main implications behind these tools. In addition, the main long-term recommendations.

1.3 Methodology

This report used literature from ProQuest (e-books and e-journals) to analyze and implement the analysis tools. This report used online magazines, newspapers, and e-journals from various sources to collect the latest news and statistics. A focus was placed on trusted and popular sources.

1.4 Structure

In addition to the introduction, conclusion, and list of references, the main body discussion includes the following sections:

1. In the first section, Zara's vision, mission, current strategy, and revenue for the past three years are examined.
2. The second and third sections contain the external and internal factors affecting Zara, incorporating theoretical strategic management tools to analyze the tool and the company's response.
3. The fourth section includes recommendations and implications of these tools.

Section 1: Zara's vision, mission, current strategy, and the last three years' revenue.

SECTION 1: ZARA'S VISION, MISSION, CURRENT STRATEGY, AND REVENUE FOR THE PAST THREE YEARS ARE EXAMINED

1.1 Vision

Visions are fundamental for social innovation, and visions are needed to create and evolve. A vision remains a vision without a strategy on how to achieve it, thereby having no impact (Rothauer, 2018). Zara's vision statement is "**to contribute to the sustainable development of society and that of the environment with which we interact**". Zara's vision focuses on business sustainability by having sustainable raw materials and competitive advantage. Zara focuses on eco-friendly operations and contributes to social development to become an environmental-friendly environment.

1.2 Mission

The mission is the basis for developing strategy, defining critical success factors, exploring key opportunities, choosing resource allocations and pleasing customers and stakeholders (Jaffe, et al., 1993). Zara's mission is to "**give customers what they want and get it to them faster than anyone else**" (ZARA, 2022). This vision reflects the company's implementation of the Fast Fashion model, which integrated different activities: the shortest supply chain (design to retail cycle), reducing inventory twice a week.

1.3 Current Strategy

To achieve the vision and mission, Zara implemented its strategy and objectives. The strategy is intended to create a competitive advantage. In contrast, a firm's ability to maintain a competitive advantage is determined by how its capabilities and resources depreciate or become obsolete over time. Therefore, companies' resources, capabilities, and strategies play a significant role in whether they succeed or fail (Jeyarathmm, 2007). In democratizing couture and bringing trendy, affordable items to the masses, Zara has revolutionized the fashion industry through its fast-fashion strategy (Sull & Turcon, 2008). To achieve the fast fashion strategy, Zara adopted a vertical integration model to help the company take control of the whole operation and maintain its sustainable competitive advantages.

1.4 Zara's last three years' revenue

Zara's net sales have grown steadily since founded and in 2019 showed a significant improvement. However, the [Net sales of the Inditex Group worldwide from 2013 to 2020, by format \(in a million euros\)](#) (Statista, 2022), shows the last two years' sales revenue for Zara, and it shows there is an aggressive decline in Zara review sales in 2020. From 2013 to 2020, Zara had the highest net sales of the whole Inditex Group worldwide, with more than 14 billion euros. However, in 2020, Inditex Group sales declined across all segments due to the Covid-19 crisis (Inditex, 2022). Also, by clicking on [Zara's brand value worldwide from 2016 to 2021](#) (Statista, 2022), the revenue declined again in 2021.

Therefore, there is a need to examine the factors affecting the company's performance (adopted from (Jeyarathmm, 2007):

1 External Environment

1.2 Porter's Five Forces Model

1.3 External Factor Analysis Summary (EFAS)

2 Internal Environment

2.2 Valuable, Rare, Inimitable, and Organizational-oriented (VIRO) framework

2.3 Internal Factor Analysis Summary (IFAS)

SECTION 2: EXTERNAL ENVIRONMENT ANALYSIS

External Environment Analysis: The environment of any organization is the sum of all conditions, events, and influences that surround and affect it. The environment consists of many factors originating from different sources, and it is complex. Environments are dynamic as they are constantly changing. As a result, environments are profoundly impacting organizations. Analyzing the external environment identifies opportunities and threats.

2.1 Porter's Five Forces Model summarized by Porter (1979) and its contribution to Zara

In an industry, groups of companies offer similar products and services that can be substituted for each other. Strategists analyze competitive forces within an industry to identify opportunities and threats to a firm. Michael develops a model for analyzing the industry environment. E. Porter: an authority on competitive strategy. The Five Forces Model helps managers identify and analyze competitive forces in an industry environment (Jeyarathmm, 2007).

This model focuses on five forces ([See Figure 1](#)):

Figure 1 Porter's Five Forces Model (Porter, 1979)

The threat of New Entrance (Medium): An industry's profitability can be threatened by the entry of potential competitors [_\(Jeyarathmm, 2007\)](#). According to Porter, entry into an industry is often accompanied by new capabilities, a desire to gain market share, and substantial resources. Yangtian, Founder of Shein, understood how to draw shoppers' attention in the digital world thanks to this expertise. Western fashionistas have been introduced to a Chinese "social commerce" style, which combines social media and online shopping. This has led to some spectacular results. The gross merchandise value (GMV) of Shein's platforms in 2019 was \$2.3bn, according to Zheshang Securities, a Chinese brokerage. The figure is expected to exceed \$20 billion this year [\(see figure 2\)](#). Analysts predict Shein's gross merchandise value will surpass Zara's by 2022. Earlier this month, Shein overtook Amazon as America's most downloaded shopping app [_\(Economist, 2021\)](#).

Medium contribution to Zara because [\(adopted from _\[Inditex, 2022\]\)](#):

1. Zara has already implemented an E-commerce platform.
2. Leading the market prices (Low-cost leadership and high-quality material)
3. Long-term relationship with the suppliers.
4. Friendly-eco operation system.
5. Sustainable raw materials require less cost of energy and water, leading to reducing the selling price).

Figure 2 Shein, Estimated Merchandise value in \$bn (Economist, 2021)

1. Bargaining Suppliers (Low) can raise prices or reduce the quality of purchased goods and services in the industry to exert bargaining power. Almost 97% of Zara's production comes from 12 major suppliers in Spain, Portugal, Turkey, Morocco, India, Pakistan, Vietnam, China, Brazil, and Argentina. Also, Zara has a long-term relationship with its suppliers [\(ZARA, 2022\)](#). However, during Corvid-19, the supplier's power is weak because of export obstruction, cancelling orders, and freezing shipments [\(Monash Business School, 2021\)](#).
2. Bargaining Power of Buyers (High): Companies view customers as a threat when they demand low prices or higher quality and better service through their bargaining power. The impact of buyers is high on Zara because:
 - 2.1 Also, most of the company's customers are women between 24 - 35. To reach this market, Zara stores locate their stores in town centres and areas with high concentrations of women between 18 and 44 [\(Hugos, 2020\)](#). However, during Corvid-19, women's unemployment increases during the pandemic, thus decreasing the purchasing power of Zara and the entire apparel industry. In addition, according to the U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics data, recent trends have

made it harder for American women to keep their jobs. As a result, 865,000 women left the labour force in September 2020, more than four times the number of men who left and more than three times the number of jobs women gained in the same month ([Center for American Progress, 2020](#)).

3. **Substitute Products (Medium):** Substitutes are those products that fulfil similar needs yet appear to be different ([Jeyarathmm, 2007](#)). However, even with Corvid-19, Zara products are still considered the dominant brand among their fast-fashion competitors and substitute brands. According to Inditex [_\(2022\)](#), Zara is trying to differentiate its product through sustainable raw materials such as cotton. Cotton is Zara's primary raw material and uses two types of cotton organic and recycled cotton. Organic cotton requires less water, energy, and cultivation. Recycled cotton crops require 80% less water than conventional crops; therefore, these two types reduce the cost of cotton and the selling price and provide a high-quality material.
4. **Rivalry Among existing Powers "Jockeying for position" (High):** Historically, competitors compete with one another by competing on price, introducing new products, and running aggressive advertising campaigns. Even though Zara is the market leader in the apparel industry, its sales revenue in 2020 decreased by 27.9% compared to 2019. Also, according to Fast retailing, Zara's revenue is higher by 8.3% compared to its direct competitor, UNIQLO (See Figures [3 & 4](#)) ([Fast Retailing, 2021](#)).

Company Name (Flagship Brand)	Country and Region	End of Fiscal Year	Sales (Trillion of yen)	Sales (Billions of dollar)	Change (%) (local base)
INDITEX (ZARA)	Spain	Jan. 2021	2.63	24.80	-27.9
Hennes & Mauritz	Sweden	Nov. 2020	2.39	22.48	-19.6
FAST RETAILING(UNIQLO)	Japan	Aug. 2020	2.01	18.91	-12.3
Gap	USA	Jan. 2021	1.47	13.80	-15.8
L Brands	USA	Jan. 2021	1.26	11.85	-8.3
PVH (Calvin Klein, Tommy Hilfiger)	USA	Jan. 2021	0.76	7.13	-28.0
Ralph Lauren	USA	Mar. 2020	0.65	6.16	-2.4
NEXT	UK	Jan. 2021	0.52	4.94	-17.2
AMERICAN EAGLE OUTFITTERS	USA	Jan. 2021	0.40	3.76	-12.7
Abercrombie & Fitch	USA	Jan. 2021	0.33	3.13	-13.7
Esprit	Hong Kong	Jun. 2020	0.13	1.19	-21.1

Notes: Compiled from the annual reports of the companies listed above.

*Figures calculated in yen using the end of February 2021 FX rates. (\$1=¥106.24)

Figure 3 Global Apparel Manufacturers and Retailers' Ranking in 2020 ([Fast Retailing, 2021](#)).

Note: Market Cap is calculated in yen using the end of February 2021 FX rates and stock price of each company.

Figure 4 Worldwide Apparel Manufacturer and Retailer; Ranking by Market Capitalization in 2020 ([Fast Retailing, 2021](#))

Therefore, Inditex decided to close 8.5% of the total stores and definitely, and Zara stores are impacted to face the challenge by 2020 compared to 2019 as per Statista (2022) (See [Figure 6](#)).

Figure 5 Number of Stores of the Inditex Group Worldwide from 2011 to 2020 (Statista, 2022).

2.2 Strategic Factor Analysis Summary (SFAS) Matrix (adopted from [Jeyarathmm, 2007](#))

SFAS matrix incorporates the factors gathered during environmental scanning and provides necessary information for strategy formulation. EFAS (External Factor Analysis Summary), IFAS (Internal Factor Analysis Summary), and SFAS serve as powerful analytical tools for strategic analysis. SFAS summarises an organization's strategic factors by combining external factors from EFAS and internal factors from IFAS (See Table 1).

EFAS for Zara:

External factors are divided into opportunities and threats, and an environmental assessment is structured using the External Factor Analysis Summary ([See Table 1](#)).

External Factors	Weight	Rating	Weighted Score	Comments
Opportunities				
1. Fascinated in new technology platforms to enhance company operation and sales work.	0.1	3	0.3	Zara focused more on a global expansion than on enhancing its E-commerce platform
2. All apparel corporations are affected by the pandemic negatively more than Zara.	0.05	4	0.2	The other fast fashion companies followed Zara's strategy.
3. Availability of sustainable and recyclable raw materials.	0.05	4	0.2	Fascinated R&D
4. Cotton price is below 2019 levels (World Bank Blogs, 2021).	0.05	2	0.1	Because customer demand declined, supplying of raw materials decreased.
Threats				
1. Corvid-19 Pandemic Impacts: Lockdown and flight restrictions	0.5	1	0.5	An emergent threat that the company didn't ready for it.
2. Saturation of Retailers of the clothing industry (UNIQLO is a very direct rival to Zara)	0.05	5	0.25	Vertical integration neutralized the threat.
3. Changing customer behaviour tends to save and consume less in clothes and fashion.	0.1	2	0.2	The customer tended to save. The purchasing power declined because of increased unemployment.
4. New entrance: Ex. Shein	0.1	4	0.4	Shein only sells virtually, but Zara has physical and online shopping facilities.

Total	1.00	2.14
-------	------	------

Table 1 External Factor Analysis Summary (EFAS) For Zara.

The Total weight score of Zara is 2.14, which is below the average of 3.0. Therefore, this figure indicates a poor response from Zara towards the opportunities and threats.

SECTION 3 ZARA'S INTERNAL ENVIRONMENT

The internal analysis identifies strengths and weaknesses so that the firm can take advantage of opportunities and avoid threats. An organizational analysis is also known as internal scanning, and it is concerned with identifying and developing corporate resources, and

Competitive advantage [\(Jeyarathmm, 2007\)](#).

Four key ways to lower costs and differentiate are efficiency, quality, innovation, and customer responsiveness, and to develop these dimensions of competitive advantage, we need competencies, resources, and capabilities [\(Jeyarathmm, 2007\)](#). Often, Zara comes out of the gate first and offers virtually the same products, made with less expensive fabric, at a lower price than the high-fashion houses. Zara's system must deal with about 300,000 stock-keeping units (SKUs) every year since most garments come in five to six colours and five to seven sizes [\(Ferdows, et al., 2005\)](#)

3.1 Resources

The resources are the inputs to the production process and serve as the basis for analysis. According to Bonfour [\(2003\)](#), there are only three resources: physical resources, human resources, and organizational resources. Additionally, Grant (1991, cited in [\(Bounfour, 2003\)](#)) discusses financi, physical, human, technological, reputation, and organizational resources.

Tangible Resources and Intangible Resources factors (adopted from [\(Inditex, 2022\)](#)); (Mihm, 2010); [\(ZARA, 2022\)](#):

3.1.1 Tangible Resources:

1. Own factories.
2. Ten logistic Centers in Spain.
3. More than 2000 stores worldwide.

4. Sustainable raw material
5. 28 external laboratories
6. Financial assets

3.1.2 Intangible Resources:

1. Fast Fashion market leader
2. Vertical Integration model
3. Fascinated Inventory system.
4. Workforce: In 2020, 12,666 employees will be in Spain ([See Figure 6](#)). As per Statista, the number of employees increased by 2.1% comparing to 2019. However, Zara's revenue declined by 27.78% in the same period as per the same source ([Inditex: net sales worldwide by format 2020 | Statista](#)) (Statista, 2022). Also, the Inditex group employees figure reduces dramatically by 18.4 % in the same period ([See Figure 7](#)). Therefore, the company might increase its business focus on the Zara brand more than others since 69% of the group's revenue comes from Zara.

Figure 6 Number of employees of Zara employees in Spain from 2011 to 2020 (Statista, 2022)

Figure 7 Number of employees of the Inditex Group worldwide from 2010 to 2020 (Statista, 2022)

5. Technological forces: In a highly competitive environment, technology proves to be a strategic weapon. Technology has profoundly affected business in terms of improved products, improved processing, new raw materials, and new product development. For example, Zara implemented an E-commerce or online sales platform in 2010. As a result, according to Inditex's E-Commerce Revenue Analytics (2021), the first half of 2021 (click on the link) showed a 36% growth compared to 2019 (see Figure 8).

	2020	2019	2018	2017	2016
TURNOVER (€ MILLION)					
Net Sales	20,402	28,286	26,145	25,336	23,311
Online sales ⁽¹⁾	32%	14%	12%	10%	N.A.

Figure 8 Zara's Economic Indicators for the last five years (Zara, 2020)

6. Zara has many trademarks worldwide.
7. Logo and exclusive brands help Zara to maintain its strong identity.
8. Develop designs in the system. Inditex (Zara's parent company) has over 700 talented designers
9. Short design to retail cycle.
10. Shipping to stores requires 24-58 hours.
11. The new style requires only two weeks to arrive in store.
12. Traceability auditors to track the suppliers are 1343 auditors in 2020.
13. The prices vary by location.

3.2 Capabilities

The definition of capabilities is 'the ability of a combination of resources to perform specific tasks or activities. A capability is the ability of various resources to accomplish a task or activity, according to Grant [\(Bounfour, 2003\)](#).

A key feature of Inditex is its vertical integration of design, production, sales, and delivery. Zara's production cycle is much shorter than that of its nearest rival. An entirely new Zara garment takes about four to five weeks from design to delivery. A new version of an existing Zara model takes about two weeks. Zara launches 11,000 unique products in an average year, compared with 2,000-4,000 from H&M or Gap, America's biggest casual-fashion chain [\(Economist, 2005\)](#). Also, according to Mihm [\(2010\)](#), traditional cycles before the advent of fast fashion took about six months from design to store availability; fast fashion today means a cycle of four weeks or less.

In Zara's inventory system, historical data is used to estimate demand for each store so that sales are maximized across the board. The warehouses were then instructed to ship inventory based on the demand figure [\(MacMillan, 2006\)](#).

3.3 Evaluate Zara's Key Resources and Capabilities

While resources are the principal source of competencies for the firm, competencies are the primary source of competitive advantages [\(Bounfour, 2003\)](#).

3.3.1 Valuable, Rare, Inimitable, and Organizational-oriented (VIRO) framework:

Barney, in 1991, developed a Valuable, Rare, Inimitable, and Organizational-oriented (VIRO) framework to analyze the firm key resources. First, a resource must be valuable to the corporation, improving opportunities and naturalizing threats to its environment. The resource must be rare among competitors and imperfectly imitable, which will be costly or impossible to recreate. Finally, the resource must be non-substitutable, i.e., it cannot be substituted by a strategic equivalent. The VIRO tool helps identify and weigh the resource and capabilities to evaluate Zara's competitive advantages. Constantly, it permits the Organization's decision-makers to formulate their issue. [\(See Table 2\)](#).

The resources and capabilities gathered in several assets (adopted from [\(Inditex, 2022\)](#); [\(ZARA, 2022\)](#)):

1. **Organization's Culture:** An organization's culture refers to its values, belief system, and expectations. The organizational culture is derived from the Organization's founders based on their values. It is passed down through the generations. Both internal and external environments influence culture and demographic factors [\(Kondalkar, 2009\)](#).

2. A firm's financial assets could include cash flow, financial leverage, and capital budgeting. Cash is raised both internally and externally and allocated in different ways. The flow of cash, interest payments on borrowings, dividend warrants for equity shareholders, and repayment of external funds are other significant issues that require constant monitoring [\(Jeyarathmm, 2007\)](#).
3. Human resource issues revolve around labour costs. Provide options and help create a competitive advantage by utilizing part-time employees, contractors, job sharing, flextime, autonomous work teams, and cross-functional work teams.

Asset Category	Zara Resources& Capabilities	V	I	R	O	
	% Response	25	25	25	25	100%
Human Capital	Workforce: 12,666 employees spread worldwide. Workforce Diversity Workforce turnover ratio Training: Zara provides regular sustainability training to its purchasing teams to raise awareness about their choices' environment and social impacts. Quality designer team (700 designers) An internalized HR value chains The working atmosphere is caring for employees' well-being and professional growth.	YES	NO	YES	--	50
	Strong Business Strategy. Pricing varies by location and is competitive with its competitors. Strong R&D: ex. Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) and Integrated Stock Management System (SINT) Design to retail cycle length (five weeks) Qualified Relationship Management	YES	YES	YES	YES	100

Physical Assets	Land (One headquarter) factories logistic centres (10 logistics centres) number of stores (2000 stores) Delivery trucks Raw materials (cotton, linen and polyester) Laboratories	YES	NO	YES	--	50
Financial Assets	Share Capital Revenue Profit and cash flow Shareholdings and treasure stocks Inventory	YES	--	YES	--	50
Organization Culture	The company ranks number one worldwide in the apparel Industry Focus on sustainable & Recyclable resources Fast Fashion brand image and market leader. Business Ethics Friendly- Environment raw materials	YES	NO	YES	--	50
Total Average Response to The Internal Factors						60%

Table 2 Valuable, Rare, Inimitable, and Organizational-oriented (VIRO) framework.

The Average company response to the Internal factors is above the average (50%), which indicates that the company responds effectively to the main internal factors.

3.3.2 Internal Factors Evaluation Summary (IFES)

Internal Factors Evaluation Summary (adapted from [_\(Jeyarathmm, 2007\)](#), [_\(Inditex, 2022\)](#); [\(ZARA, 2022\)](#))

Internal factors are divided into Strengths and weaknesses, and an environmental assessment is structured using Internal Factor Analysis Summary ([See Table 3](#)).

	Internal Factors	Weight	Rating	Weight Score	Comments
Strengths	1. Global Expansion	0.1	5	0.5	Company goal.
	2. Strong Brand Image	0.1	5	0.5	Long terms strategy.
	3. Vertical Integration Model	0.05	4	0.2	Flexible model because Zara controls the entire operation
	4. Sustainable raw material	0.05	5	0.25	The company mission. Fast-changing collections.
	5. Product differentiation	0.05	4	0.2	Following the market trends
	6. Short design to retail cycle	0.05	5	0.25	To reach the consumer satisfaction
	7. Qualified designers	0.08	4	0.32	Fast response to customer demands and maintaining solid relationships with suppliers.
	8. Strong Relationship management	0.05	4	0.2	
	9. Sustainable operations.	0.05	5	0.25	The company mission.
Weaknesses	1. Low Social Media advertisement	0.2	1	0.2	The company saw that store expansion was more critical than advertisement & Online shopping.
	2. Focus on store expansion than E-commerce development.	0.15	2	0.3	
	3. Simple Operational Technology.	0.05	3	0.15	They prefer the designers to contact the stores to directly get customer feedback. To reduce the inventory stocks and doesn't give the consumer the time to wait because the stock will not be available for the second wave.
	4. Limited stock	0.02	1	0.02	
	Total	1.0		3.34	

Table 3 Internal Factors Evaluation Summary (IFES)

The Total weight score of Zara is 3.34, which is above the average of 3.0. Therefore, this figure indicates a good response from Zara regarding its strengths and weaknesses.

3.3.3 Strategic Factors Evaluation Summary

The Strategic Factors Evaluation Summary (SFAS) matrix provides a framework for formulating strategies. The following table ([See Table 4](#)) summarizes the major factors that directly affected Zara during the pandemic to evaluate how internal and external factors affected Zara's growth revenue. Unfortunately, Zara's response to the pandemic was 2.9 on the SFAS, which does not bode well for their long-term business strategy.

		Strategic Factors	Weight	Rating	Weight Score
External Factors	Opportunities	1. Fascinated in new technology platforms to enhance company operation and sales work.	0.1	3	0.3
		2. All apparel corporations are affected by the pandemic negatively more than Zara.	0.1	4	0.4
	Threats	1. Corvid-19 Pandemic Impacts: Lockdown and flight restrictions	0.5	1	0.5
		2. Changing consumer behaviour tends to save and consume less in clothes and fashion.	0.2	2	0.4
Internal Factors	Strengths	1. Global Expansion	0.1	5	0.5
		2. Strong Brand Image	0.15	5	0.3
	Weaknesses	1. Low Social Media advertisement	0.2	1	0.2
		2. Focus on store expansion than E-commerce development	0.15	2	0.3
Total			1.0		2.9

Table 4 Strategic Factors Evaluation Summary for Zara.

SECTION 4 STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT TOOLS IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

4.1 implications:

A strategic management approach has a significant role in evaluating a company's performance to meet its goals and objectives. While the tools presented in the report have several implications, they remain theoretical methods and unfortunately, there is no perfect approach to measure a company's performance acutely.

2.1.1 Porter's Five Forces Model (adopted from [\(Isabelle, et al., 2020\)](#))

- The model does not consider time dynamics, such as emergent issues.
- It is primarily focused on macro environments.
- It should be integrated with alternative strategic frameworks, such as VIRO microenvironments.

2.1.2 Strategic Factor Analysis Summary (EFAS)

- The total weight of factors needs to be equal to 1.0; measuring factors' weight and the rate is limited to 1.0.

2.1.3 VIRO Framework

- Need to combine with another quantitative analysis tool.

4.2 Recommendations:

The vertical integration of emerging issues such as Corvid-19 ([\(Jeyarathmm, 2007\)](#)) is very risky. Therefore, Zara should focus on the following areas to minimize the impact of Corvid-19 on its revenue:

1. Make social media advertisements a priority. Marketers can use social media to communicate with segmented markets almost automatically. Marketers can deliver personalised messages and information by learning about consumers' interests and lifestyles from their social networking profiles ([\(Noor et al., 2011\)](#)).
2. Social Media stars can increase a company's revenue because their followers like to emulate them.
3. To increase traffic to your online store, focus on virtual promotion (online sales) rather than physical promotion (in-store promotion).
4. Create regional social media such as (Zara Middle East Instagram) and engage with followers' comments. Most of Zara's consumers are loyal to the brand, and Zara needs a deep social media communication strategy to gain their loyalty.

5. After the pandemic, keep the expansion low by decreasing the number of stores.
6. Use the Pandemic as inspiration to create fashion designs. Women tend to wear masks that match their entire outfit. This allows Zara to produce attractive masks that match their outfits.

5. CONCLUSION:

Zara is an international fashion company. Inditex is one of the world's largest distribution groups, which owns and operates this company. Zara's fast fashion strategy relied on vertical integration, which helped it maintain its competitive advantages by controlling the whole operation. While Zara's revenue has grown consistently since its founding, its revenue drastically decreased in 2020 and 2021 due to Corvid-19. This report aims to analyze the internal and external factors influencing Zara's revenue during the Corvid-19 Pandemic. External Factor Analysis Summary Framework and Porter Five Forces Model analyze how external factors affected Zara's revenue. This analysis shows that Zara did not respond well to the external factors, which explains the continued decline in Zara revenue in 2021. In studying the Organization's internal factors using the VIRO Framework and Internal Factor Analysis Summary, Zara responded well to the internal variables. In this respect, Zara remains the market leader compared to its competitors, negatively impacted by the corvid-19 outbreak as an emergent problem. By measuring the Strategic Factors Analysis Summary Matric (SFAS), Zara's response to the internal and external factors fell within the red zone (2.9 out of 3.0) and requires a change in strategy by increasing social media advertising and combining online sales with other social media platforms. However, the tools used to measure the internal and external factors are still theoretical and may not help examine the situation practically. Many scholars are thus seeking a suitable quantitative tool that combines these tools to precisely measure the business issue.

6. BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Inditex (2022) *Who we are*. Available at: <https://www.inditex.com/en/about-us/who-we-are> (Accessed 14 January 2022).
2. Zara (2022) *Company Corporation*. Available at: <https://www.zara.com/uk/en/z-company-corp1391.html?v1=11112> (Accessed: 14 January 2022).
3. Inditex (2022) *Net sales of the Inditex Group worldwide from 2013 to 2020, by format*. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/456505/sales-inditex-group-worldwide-by-format/> (Accessed: 14 January 2022)
4. Statista (2022) *Zara's brand value worldwide from 2016 to 2021*. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/980126/brand-value-of-zara-worldwide/> (Accessed 14 January 2022).
5. Inditex (2021)' *Second-quarter revenue, profits and cash hit historic highs, First-half 2021 results*. Available at :[b39b9670-f97e-d856-dd24-46920ccda3e5 \(inditex.com\)](https://www.inditex.com/press-releases/2021/08/16/second-quarter-revenue-profits-and-cash-hit-historic-highs) (Accessed: 14 January 2022).
6. Jeyarathmm, M. (2007), *Strategic Management. Global Media*. Available from: ProQuest Ebook Central. [14 January 2022].
7. Sull, D., Turconi, S. (2008) 'Fast fashion lessons', *London Business School Summer 2008*, pp.2-8. Available at: <https://www.london.edu/-/media/files/publications/bsr/fast-fashion-lessons.pdf?la=en> (Accessed: 15 January 2022).
8. The Economist (2005) *The future of fast fashion*. Available at: <https://www.economist.com/business/2005/06/16/the-future-of-fast-fashion> (Accessed 16 January 16, 2022).
9. The Economist (2021) *Shein exemplifies a new style of Chinese multinational*. Available at: <https://www.economist.com/business/shein-exemplifies-a-new-style-of-chinese-multinational/21805217> (Accessed: 16 January 2022).
10. Inditex (2015) *Inditex-Press Dossier*. Available a: <https://www.inditex.com/documents/10279/269733/Press+dossier/2a9786bb-c900-4d12-9682-4cd4b161df2a?version=1.0> (Accessed: 16 January 2022).

11. Inditex (2021) *Inditex-Press Kit*. Available at: <https://www.inditex.com/documents/10279/249245/Inditex+Press+Kit+2021.pdf/615b517b-a253-fd93-6126-4cee6fa2001d> (Accessed 16 January 2022).
12. Hugos, H. (2020) *Zara's unique business model is driven by its supply chain capabilities*. Issued 4 January. Available at: <https://www.scmglobe.com/zara-clothing-company-supply-chain/#:~:text=The%20company%20purchases%20raw%20fabric,suppliers%20are%20mostly%20by%20truck> (Accessed: 16 January, 2022).
13. Fast Retailing (2021). *Industry Ranking*. Available at: <https://www.fastretailing.com/eng/ir/direction/position.html> (Accessed: 17 January 2022).
14. Zara 2022, *Suppliers*. Available at: <https://www.zara.com/uk/en/sustainability-suppliers-mkt1456.html> (Accessed: 17 January 2022).
15. Ferdows, K., Lewis, M., Machuca, J. (2005) 'Zara's Secret for Fast Fashion', *Harvard Business Review*. Available at: <https://hbswk.hbs.edu/archive/zara-s-secret-for-fast-fashion> (Accessed: 17 January 2022).
16. Zara (2020), *Inditex group annual report*. Available at: [https://static.zara.net/static/joinlife/2020 Inditex Annual Report.pdf](https://static.zara.net/static/joinlife/2020%20Inditex%20Annual%20Report.pdf) (Accessed 18 January 2022).
17. Statista (2022), *Zara's brand value worldwide from 2016 to 2021*. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/674434/number-of-zara-stores-worldwide-by-region/> (Accessed: 18 January 2022).
18. Mihm, B. (2010) 'Fast Fashion in A Flat World: Global Sourcing Strategies', *International Business & Economics Research Journal (IBER)*, 9(6). Doi: 10.19030/iber.v9i6.585.
19. Macmillan, A. (2006) 'Research collaboration and math model guided intern through 'fast fashion' world', *MIT News*. Available at: <https://news.mit.edu/2006/lfm-correa-1220> (Accessed 18 January 2022).
20. Center for American Progress (2020), *How COVID-19 Sent Women's Workforce Progress Backward*. Available at: <https://www.americanprogress.org/article/covid-19-sent-womens-workforce-progress-backward/> (Accessed: 20 January 2022).
21. World Bank Blogs (2021), *Agricultural raw materials prices weaken amid COVID-19*. Available at: <https://blogs.worldbank.org/opendata/agricultural-raw-materials-prices-weaken-amid-covid-19> (Accessed: 20 January 2022).

22. Brennan, L. & Sisk, F. (2014), 'Strategic Management: A Practical Guide', *Business Expert Press*. New York. Available at: ProQuest Ebook Central (Accessed: 14 January 2022).
23. Rothauer, D. (2018), *Vision and Strategy: Strategic Thinking for Creative and Social Entrepreneurs*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH, Basel/Berlin/Boston. Available from: ProQuest Ebook Central (Accessed:14 January 2022).
24. Jaffe, D., Tobe, G. & Tobe, G. (1993), 'Organizational Vision, Values and Mission', *Course Technology Crisp*. Menlo Park. Available from: ProQuest Ebook Central (Accessed: 14 January 2022).
25. Poter, M. (1979) '*How competitive forces shape strategy*, *Harvard Business Review*. Available at: <https://hbr.org/1979/03/how-competitive-forces-shape-strategy> (Accessed 12 January 2022).
26. Monash Business School (2021), *Global garment industry bears the brunt of Corvid supply chain woes*. Available at: <https://tinyurl.com/4b4v62zh> (Accessed: 17 January 2022).
27. Kondalkar, V. (2009), 'Organization Development', *New Age International Ltd*. Daryaganj. Available from: ProQuest Ebook Central (Accessed: 17 January 2022).
28. Bounfour, A. (2003), *The Management of Intangibles: The Organization's Most Valuable Assets*. Taylor & Francis Group, Florence. Available at: ProQuest Ebook Central (Accessed: 17 January 2022).
29. Isabelle, D., Horak, K., McKinnon, S., Palumbo, C. (2020) 'Is Porter's Five Forces Framework Still Relevant? A study of the capital/labour intensity continuum via mining and IT industries', *Technology Innovation Management Review*. vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 28-41.
30. Noor, A., & Hendricks, J. (2011), *Social media: Usage and Impact*. Lexington Books, Lanham, MD. Available from: ProQuest Ebook Central. [13 January 2022].